

A DUAL MICROPROCESSOR DIGITAL ACQUISITION
RECORDING SYSTEM¹

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ABSTRACT

A discussion of dual microprocessors in a split-bus configuration to acquire and record sensor data and how this architecture is applied to a recording system is the objective of this paper. The data is collected using several kinds of expendable probes deployed from ship and aircraft platforms. These self-contained units automatically acquire and record the information received and provide basic operational facilities including optional programming, real time digital display and status items as well as system self tests.

The function of data storage is provided by cassette recording. There are also external strip chart outputs as well as data transmission capabilities within these systems.

To the user, these systems offer a simple operating task and are flexible enough to apply to different variations in data acquisition requirements.

to the specific operating and user requirements. Both systems had to satisfy design criteria unique to each platform as well as those requirements common to the two operating environments. Specifically, both systems had to be lightweight, self-contained (a single unit item), flexible, easy to operate, requiring minimal set up time, and automatic in operation. In addition to the primary data it was to record, an array of displaying, printing, recording functions, and the ability to acquire other auxiliary data were needed. These design goals alone were reason to develop and utilize this type of system configuration and microprocessor architecture applied in these two systems.

System Configuration

To accomplish these types of operating functions and requirements in both systems, two microprocessors utilized in a split bus configuration were adopted. This split bus configuration allows both processors to operate independantly and without regard to what the other may actively be doing in the system. Each processor is assigned an overall primary task and programmed to accomplish the task in the most expedient manner possible. Important in data acquisition systems are the ability to provide flexible and yet concise operating elements; specifically, ease of operation and clear controls and data presentations.

Shown in Figures 1 and 2 respectively are the shipboard and airborne system block diagrams. The primary differences, as can be seen, are the specific sensor interfaces (front end), front panel controls and sequences (with some similarity), and the operating system program (very similar between the two systems). These differences will be discussed in more detail in the specific sections related to each system.

Each system contains the same basic elements of signal interfacing, data transferring and data recording, printing, and display. Both systems contain a data memory block which is common to each processor aside from the local program and scratch pad memory of each processor. This provides the link between the two processors for data transfer (or passing) and processor to processor communications.

For the operating processors, the MC6800 microprocessor³ manufactured by Motorola Inc., was

Introduction

One of the U.S. Naval Oceanographic Office mission requirements is to collect and process ocean environment data. Specific to this requirement is the acquisition and processing of ocean temperature and sound velocity. This is accomplished by using both airborne and shipboard survey platforms. In the area of airborne expendable sensors, the AN/SSQ-36 Bathythermograph Transmitter Set² provides the temperature profile while shipboard sensors include a number of variations to the expendable bathythermograph probe (XBT) for temperature profiles and the new expendable sound velocity (XSV) profiler developed by the Sippican Corp., Marion, Mass.

Background

These requirements necessitated an instrument both in airborne and shipboard operating environments to acquire and record high resolution data for computer processing and analysis. Because of the diverse operating and user environments of both airborne and shipboard platforms, two systems of a similar configuration were designed and fabricated. Each system was tailored

Figure 1: Shipboard System Block Diagram

selected because of its memory mapped I/O architecture and the way two of these processors will work in this configuration. This memory mapped I/O architecture was chosen rather than the vectored I/O architecture found in many 8-bit processor families by virtue of the fact that the peripheral devices themselves are treated as memory locations to the operating processor. This affords advantages in both programming and operation of the processors themselves.

The MC6800 utilizes a two-phase clock for operation. The first cycle or phase one is an instruction or data fetch cycle while the second cycle or phase two is the execute cycle. The system clock (1 MHz) provides the necessary two phase clock that both processors require with one important difference. The phase one clock of one processor becomes the phase two clock of the other processor and the converse. In effect, both processors are operating out-phase ($\frac{1}{2}$ cycle in fetch or execution) to each other. When one processor is in a fetch cycle (program or data element fetch) the other processor is in an execute cycle (execution on program or data). It can be seen from this scheme that neither processor can read or write to the same or different memory segments at the same time despite having memory segments that are common to the two processors. In addition, bus arbitration and bus contention are completely eliminated as compared to applications of multiprocessor single or common bus oriented systems. Again, noting the system configuration diagrams, we see both processors are on a split or separate bus, each operating self-contained to

each other. In the figures, the left most processor is designated the acquisition processor. The acquisition processor's primary function is to acquire and store digital data in memory and operate in a polling mode. Polling is simply sequentially querying the device for service. The processor controls various operating states of the system, the sampling function, and proper control to the specific interfaces and front panel indicators. The right most processor is designated the output processor. It's primary function is to control the output devices in the displaying, printing, recording, and external transmission of digital data as well as responding to operator inputs and requests through the keyboard device. It operates in an interrupt mode. The interrupt function is a request for service requiring an immediate response from the controlling processor.

General Operation

The basic operation of this configuration is separated into sequential blocks. The acquisition processor (UP-1) as briefly mentioned before, identifies operational states and responds with front panel displays, acquires the data, and stores the data in the data memory block. The output processor (UP-2) upon message interpretations from UP-1, recognizes operational states, displays in real time the data being sampled, records the data, and responds to operator commands or requests. A general operation in both systems would progress in this fashion. Upon recognition of probe deployment, UP-1 would signal to UP-2 that data is being

Figure 2: Airborne System Block Diagram

acquired. UP-1 is acquiring the data (the sampling function) at intervals programmed by the operator and controlled by an interval timing element. UP-2 begins displaying sampled data at intervals of once per second. The timing function is controlled by the real time clock. Upon recognition of one of several terminating conditions, UP-1 concludes acquisition and returns to await probe deployment. UP-2 is signaled that the acquisition mode has ended and now begins recording the data which was stored by UP-1 during the acquisition mode. Processing, printing, and transmission functions are also accomplished during this time. Once complete, UP-2 reverts to a standby operation until the acquisition mode is entered into again. This basic operation is straight forward and uncomplicated by the operation of both processors. It is obvious that other operations and functions by both processors can and do happen. Examples are auxiliary data acquisition by UP-2 during probe deployment, pre- and post-processing by UP-1, and data formatting by both processors.

Shipboard System Specifics

The shipboard system was specifically designed to acquire XBT and XSV data, however because of the front end configuration, other probes or analog signals can be used or applied. Operational characteristics on the platform require the system to automatically enter the acquisition mode

during probe deployment, thus providing a totally hands-off operation. Additionally, set up functions such as sample rates, probe types, and operational selections are simple and non-repetitive for input on every deployment. In this particular shipboard configuration application, the existing analog recording system (an MK-2A Recorder⁴) is enhanced by using it to provide a hard copy output response (strip chart function) of the data. This is accomplished by computing and providing a synthesized signal to the existing recording system. Other specifics include several different sample rates (which can be synchronized with other equipment), a second-difference computation and JJXX format⁵ listing, formatted data transmission, and system self test features.

Airborne System Specifics

The airborne system differs from the shipboard system in that the airborne platform requires a three channel acquisition system for use with expendable probes. The main reason for the expanded capability is the increased deployment rate of the sensors themselves. Because survey aircraft cover a larger area and at a faster rate, probe deployment is more rapid and this requirement necessitates each data acquisition channel to be asynchronous and independent in operation. Within the overall system however, the basic operations for both processors are the same as in the shipboard system. An important characteristic in

this system is the type of signal being digitized. The AN/SSQ-36, when active in the water, transmits to the aircraft a frequency modulated signal which is directly proportional to the temperature sensor element. Hence, sampling is accomplished by determining the period of this waveform. The results are then directly related to temperature. Other features of this system include providing more hardware output capabilities such as strip chart outputs and scope monitor functions. The auxiliary data which is acquired in this system by UP-2 is present positional data that can be selected by the operator from two navigation systems within the aircraft. Specifically, the LTN-72, Litton Systems and the GNS-500, Global Navigation continuously update the navigation information within the system and upon entering a channel acquisition mode, is acquired by UP-2 and added to the data block to provide positional information to that particular data segment.

General System Discussion

As previously mentioned, both systems contain the same basic elements. Primary data storage is provided by use of a cassette recorder. This recorder is of the incremental type (character by character) allowing more control by the processor for data recording and playback. The alphanumeric display unit provides up to 32 characters of display for data presentations, system status responses, and used by the system for messages oriented towards a user-friendly approach. A 20-character thermal alphanumeric printer supplies hard copy records of data items and listings of processed data. Its flexibility includes inverting and non-inverting character formats as well as extended characters for highlighted listings. External communications are handled through an RS-232C interface^o configured transmission port. Designed as a computer link for data up-loads, the system and this port relieves the burden of data acquisition by the local data acquisition/data processing computer. The system operating programs (both airborne and shipboard) are ROM (read only memory) based and therefore self-booting. Both systems contain self-tests for fault isolation.

Shown in Figure 5. are the specific minimum requirements and features that were needed and provided in these two systems. These requirements stem from the operational platforms that are utilized. In Figure 8. are the specific feature differences of the two systems. Again, the operational considerations and platforms were the driving criteria.

Deployments

The airborne system (prototype) is routinely deployed on Naval Oceanographic RP-3A survey aircraft stationed at Patuxent River NAS, Maryland. A special deployment took place on a Navy P-3C aircraft at Barbers Point NAS, Hawaii. In the latter deployment, the system capability for minimum installation and training requirements along with its stand-alone feature resulted in adopting it well to this specialized aircraft.

Figure 3: RP-3A Airborne Survey Platform

The Naval Oceanographic Office shipboard pre-production unit is presently in test and evaluation on survey platforms USNS KANE, TAGS-27, and USNS SILAS BENT, TAGS-26. Two additional preproduction shipboard units were installed aboard ships-of-opportunity for the Meteorological Oceanographic Equipment Program and the Fleet Numerical Oceanographic Center, Monterey, California. Two other shipboard preproduction units were delivered and installed on the USS MOOSEBRUGGER, DD-980. Again, various operational disciplines were confronted and easily adopted as a result of the capabilities of these systems. This split bus multiprocessor configuration can no doubt be utilized in other system applications and functions that are yet to be determined in the oceanographic community and to other areas of discipline.

Figure 4: Shipboard Survey Platform USNS KANE, TAGS-27

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to thank God in Heaven for grace and strength in working on this project. To Robert Broome, Physical Oceanography Branch and Gary Athey, Project Support Branch, Naval Oceanographic Office, for their suggestions and encouragement. To Bill Pierce and the staff at Computer Sciences Corporation, for his technical involvement and their efforts on the preproduction units and drawing package. To Tom Wilson, electronic technician, Naval Oceanographic Office, who through patience and skill fabricated, assembled, and debugged the prototype and preproduction units. To Bob Betcher, Naval Oceanographic Office, who guided this engineer through the joys and pains of preproduction. Also, to John Selleck and Andy Watkins for their contribution and to Barbara Lee and Gail Calvert for their efforts.

REFERENCES

1. Patent application entitled, "A Split-Bus Multiprocessor System," Navy Case No. 65,928; pp. 1-15.
2. The Sippican Corporation, "A High Accuracy Air Launched XBT," Conference Record, Oceans '81; (IEEE Publication Number 81CH1685-7); pp. 363-367.
3. Motorola, Inc., Microcomputer Data Library, 1980; Section 1, pp. 1-35.
4. The Sippican Corporation, Instruction Manual for the Expendable Bathythermograph System; Revised 1975; Sections 1 through 6.
5. NAVWEASERVFAC Pensacola, Programmed Instruction - Evaluating and Encoding Bathythermographic (BT) Data, NWS-AG-A-050, October 1978; pp. 1-43.
6. Electronic Industries Association, Interface Between Data Terminal Equipment and Data Communication Equipment Employing Serial Binary Data Interchange, EIA Standard RS-232-C, August 1969; pp. 1-29.

- USER PROGRAMMABLE
 - SAMPLE RATE
 - FALL RATE
 - PROBE DEPTH
- STANDARD MESSAGE FORMAT (CASSETTE)
 - JULIAN DATE
 - XBT NUMBER
 - DROP TIME
 - POSITION
 - SEA SFC TEMP
 - BOTTOM DEPTH
 - SAMPLE RATES
 - PROBE TYPE
 - FALL RATE
 - COMMENTS
- INFLECTION POINT
 - PROCESSED
 - FORMATTED
 - PRINT-OUT
- AUTO START
 - MINIMUM OPERATOR INTERVENTION
- 20 CHARACTER PRINTER
- 32 CHARACTER DISPLAY
- CASSETTE RECORDER
- REAL TIME CLOCK
- EDITING CAPABILITIES
- 20% EXPANSION
- PLAYBACK FEATURE
- BUILT-IN TESTS (BIT)
- COMMON COMPONENTS
 - 80% INTERCHANGABLE
- MINIMUM INSTALLATION
 - RACK MOUNTED
- MINIMUM OPERATING REQ'TMS
- MINIMUM TRAINING REQ'TMS
- AUXILIARY OUTPUTS
 - PLOTTER PORT
 - RS 232 PORT
- OPERATOR KEYBOARD

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|--|---|
| <p>SHIP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NO SYSTEM MODS. REQUIRED ● EXPANDABLE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> XSV XBT/XSV SHEAR PROBE ● INTERFACE EXISTING RECORDER ● SAMPLE RATE TO 60/SEC. | <p>AIR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3 CHANNEL INPUT-ASYNCHRONOUS ● SAMPLE RATE TO 20/SEC. ● RECORDS FREQUENCY ● 3 CHANNEL SCOPE MONITOR |
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Figure 8: Shipboard/Airborne System Unique Features

Figure 5: Shipboard/Airborne System Common Features

Figure 6: Shipboard System Function Block Diagram

Figure 9: Airborne System Function Block Diagram

Figure 7: Shipboard System Preproduction Unit

Figure 10: Airborne System Prototype